

To reconstitute the Bruker data sets:

- Create a folder with the name ending in .d
- Create a subfolder with the name ending in .m
- Drop the scan.xml and the ser files in the .d folder
- Drop the apexAcquisition.method file in the .m subfolder
- Rename the files by removing the prefixes. The only filenames should be: ser, scan.xml, and apexAcquisition.method

These are all the files you need to reconstitute a data set that can be manipulated with SPIKE.

